

مركز قيادة
قوات السلطان المسلحة

HEAD QUARTERS
SULTAN'S ARMED FORCES
P.O. Box 602, MUSCAT,
OMAN

20 Dec 72

Dear Andrew,

Many thanks for your letter of
02 Nov 72. I'm so sorry that this is probably
too late to reach you before you depart for
home. I've been meaning to write ever since
I attended a meeting of the Association Council
at which Karen Fifelt was present just
after her arrival and your expedition was
discussed. Bill Peyton, who had arranged
the Harvard side of things, was there to
lobby for them and he was delighted to
find that I had been corresponding with
you and could lobby for you. So all was
approved, and I assume that you will arrive
with them in about 7 days time.
I'm so looking forward to seeing you
all, and I have a trip to Sohar planned
for the following week-end with a cousin
of one of the local Sheikhs.

In haste,
With best wishes for Christmas
and New Year,

Yours sincerely,

David Hoall